

Agro2Circular

D7.11 – A2C circular Action Plan report

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1 List of abbreviations

A2C: Agro2Circular

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

CARM: Autonomous Community of the Region of Murcia

TTCCs: Technological Centers

CE: Circular Economy

CEAP: Circular Economy Action Plan

EIP-Agri: European innovation partnership for agricultural productivity and sustainability

ERDF: European Regional Development Fund

INFO: Development Agency of the Region of Murcia

PERTE: Strategic Projects for Economic Recovery and Transformation

RIS4 Region of Murcia: Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart and Sustainable Specialization of the Region of Murcia 2021-2027 (RIS4)

R&D: Research and Development

SAT: Self-Assessment Tool

SMEs: Small and medium-sized enterprises

2 Executive summary <abstract>

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project has been designed to promote the territorial development of circular solutions by providing tools and knowledge on how to implement these solutions. The project activities related to this task (T.7.5.6) and deliverable (D.7.11) have focused on providing concrete actions in line with the results obtained through the multidimensional model, which involved the participation of the different stakeholders, and in which the needs and barriers that hinder the development of circular solutions in the agri-food industry were systematically identified, analysed and addressed.

A synthesis report has been achieved that describes the cluster CEAP (Circular Economy Action Plan) for the territorial deployment of circular systemic solutions in the Region of Murcia.

This document includes the actions that can be implemented in the Region of Murcia and that could be extrapolated to other regions for the development of circular solutions in the agri-food industry. In the deliverable D.7.10 it was considered that different regions or cities may have unique cultural and contextual factors, which influence the data that can be collected and with which to design a CEAP. Under this premise and to enrich the innovative agri-food ecosystem, the CEAP designed not only includes actions that could take place in the territory of the Region of Murcia but also includes the interconnection with the national and European spheres.

It is noteworthy that AGROFOOD cluster, together with the contribution of CARM and INFO, as key stakeholders in the agri-food sector in the Region of Murcia, has developed the following document, using the knowledge acquired in recent years thanks to participation in the A2C project. AGROFOOD partner has carried out the work of bringing together regional information, but also monitoring similar actions in other regions to implement the CE. This document presents and evaluates the results collected in conversations held with managers, technicians, public research bodies, regional administration and associations related to the CE, as well as monitoring information on websites to find out the current status of other similar Action Plans and Programs and Strategies for the period 2021-2027.

During the first stage of the execution of the A2C Project, different documents were evaluated, including the Murcia Region ERDF Program 2021-2027, the Strategic Plan of the Region of Murcia 2022-2027 and the Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart and

Sustainable Specialization of the Region of Murcia 2021-2027 (RIS4 Region of Murcia). The information included in the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy "Spain 2030" and the Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia 2030 were also taken into account.

In a second phase, the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) together with the A2C multidimensional model (D7.10) have been other tools for the roadmap for designing this CEAP of the Region of Murcia, together with the main Programmes and Strategies for the period 2021-2027. In this time, a SWOT analysis has been made for linking the information, which allowed as a result having concrete actions gathered in the CEAP.

The results of the A2C multidimensional model were used to minimize the complexity associated with implementation. These are eight dimensions that cover a wide range of aspects, which have been simplified in the Action Lines for sustainable waste production and management: Improving Critical Mass and Internationalization; Improving Human Capital, Training and Education; Improving Governance and Access to Financing and; Improving Standardization and Legislation. The document indicates 21 actions to achieve a total of 7 identified targets broken down into 76 available solutions.

This CEAP represents a comprehensive approach to transform Murcia's economic model. By integrating circularity into the agri-food sector, the plan aims to close resource cycles, reduce waste and maximise the value derived from agricultural and industrial processes. This is especially important in a region where the agri-food sector generates a substantial volume of organic by-products, which can be valorised into new ingredients for the food sector for human or animal feed, or nutraceuticals or cosmetics, biofertilisers, bioplastics or renewable energy. These initiatives not only contribute to the preservation of the environment, but also create new economic opportunities, further consolidating the sector's leadership.

3 Introduction

The Circular Economy (CE) approach is inextricably linked with the development of innovation, creation of new business models and society's increasing environmental awareness, which in effect contributes to increasing the competitiveness of the Region of Murcia economy in relation to our partners from other parts of Europe and the world. At the end of 2015, the European Commission published Closing the loop communication: an EU action plan for the CE. The document outlined proposals for policies to facilitate the shift in the economic development model to be implemented by the EU in the upcoming years. These actions focus on several priority areas such as plastics, food waste, critical raw materials, demolition and construction waste, and biomass and biomass products. The Communication highlights the role of innovation in the transition to CE.

The economies of the EU Member States are different and therefore there is no one suitable model for the transition to CE for all of them. Therefore, the conclusions of the meeting of EU ministers at the June 2016 Environment Council proposed that Member States, following the guidance of the European Commission, should develop national programmes for the transition to CE. It is essential that this new model of economic development is implemented at all levels – starting with the EU, its Member States, and ending with the province and municipality level. This document is obligatory in terms of scope of action at the national level¹.

The main European frameworks that justify the importance of the (EC) are:

- EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (2020): Defines priority actions to move towards a sustainable Europe, addressing sectors such as plastics, food waste and biomass.
- European Green Deal: Key strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, promoting circular models in industry and agriculture.

¹ Comunicación de la Comisión Europea "Cerrar el círculo: un plan de acción de la UE para la economía circular" (COM/2015/0614 final)

- Agenda 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG): Highlights the urgent need to implement the circular economy as a means to face global challenges, improve efficiency and reduce environmental impacts.
- Circularity in the EU circular economy bill proposal within the joint roadmap for decarbonization and competitiveness of the recently launched EUs Competitiveness Compass
- Circularity and access to materials from the draft EU industrial plan, The Clean Industrial Deal

In this sense, in meetings with stakeholders, the Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia is discussed with lines of action known from other strategies but focused on CE of the agri-food sector.

With them, the Agro2Circular project has planned actions to help circularity in the agri-food sector. These actions are resources to apply the principles of the CE and achieve the objective of “increasing the deployment of circular solutions, to ensure effective widespread uptake and high visibility of circular systemic solutions that serve as a reference for other regions”.

So, the Murcia Region's Circular Economy Action Plan for the agri-food sector focuses on the key points that need to be improved to promote adoption, replication and scalability in the sector.

The partner AGROFOOD has evaluated resources and knowledge enabling both to address the agrifood sector main challenges (reducing food & plastics waste and increasing the level of digitalization), as well as to effectively deploy and replicate the CE. A CEAP for A2C project has been progressively constructed at task 7.5.6 and based on the territorial multidimensional analysis from WP7. In addition, task 8.6, where a Directory of Good Practices for Circular Economy in the agrifood sector has been elaborated, has served to detect tools used by success stories and to be able to transfer them to an Action Plan. Finally, the proposed CEAP is in line with the regional initiative to address regional challenges.

In alignment with that strategy, this deliverable is framed under the WP7 “A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability” and WP8 “A2C outreach: Communication, dissemination, exploitation, training & policy recommendations”, specifically related with tasks “7.1. Public Engagement”, “7.4 Social and economic analysis”, “7.5 Multidimensional

model for adoption, replicability and scalability of A2C systemic solution at regional and EU level (7.5.6 Self-assessment tool elaboration) & “8.6 Training, knowledge transfer and guidelines/recommendations to promote A2C circular model”. Moreover, it is linked with the project objectives number 2 “to provide the A2C technological solution the circular systemic approach by building a multidimensional model enabling the solution territorial deployment and its replication and scalability (with relevant stakeholders)” and number 3 “To maximize project impacts and facilitating A2C systemic solution replication& scalability”. The implementation of the CE in the agri-food sector represents an opportunity for it, but presents challenges and difficulties identified in the diagnosis carried out with the data collected from the SAT and represented in a SWOT analysis. Specifically, it has been possible to determine the strategic priorities based on the self-knowledge reflected in the surveys carried out and the SWOT analysis. This information, obtained thanks to the use of the SAT developed in the A2C project, has been the roadmap to define the actions that form part of the CEAP presented.

In summary, D.7.11, together with deliverables D7.3, D7.10 & D8.7, is the final output of the work carried out in task 7.5 for the CEAP in the agrifood sector of the Region of Murcia.

This document includes the List of abbreviations, Executive summary <abstract> and Introduction, and after the formal sections, the document begins with section 4, titled “Background to implement the CE in the Region of Murcia” and continues with section 5 “SWOT Circular Economy in the agri-food sector” and section 6, titled “Circular Economy Action Plan for agri-food sector in the Region of Murcia”. This section details the proposed actions to facilitate the implementation of the CE in the agri-food sector of the Region of Murcia. The deliverable concludes with Section 7 “Conclusions” and Section 8 References, where the main comments and scope, as well as limitations and future recommendations, are presented; besides the links of interest.

Knowledge of the sector and success stories already implemented in the agri-food sector (D8.6 & D8.7), as well as the “A2C multidimensional model (D7.10)” tool (specific SAT tool), have been used to define the optimal actions that should be integrated into the CEAP.

The Region of Murcia is in a privileged position to create a model of sustainable growth that can inspire other regions. The leadership of the agri-food sector in Murcia is linked through this Action Plan to a commitment to the CE.

4 Background to implement the CE in the Region of Murcia

It must be stressed that the Region of Murcia does not have to start from scratch. The public administration as well as scientific institutions and entrepreneurs have been implementing different activities and initiatives related to CE for many years now. The General Directorate of Environment of the CARM was responsible for launching the Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia 2017-2030, for which there was public consultation and which is serving as a guide to carry out different actions (<https://participa.carm.es/procesos-deliberativos/proceso?item=101>).

In addition, from the Region of Murcia, there are several entities involved in promoting the CE, with the CARM from its different ministries being responsible for its promotion and using as instruments: the Circular Economy Strategy of the Region of Murcia itself; the Waste Plan of the Region of Murcia 2016-2020 extended until 2022; Law 7/2022, of April 8, on waste and contaminated soils for a circular economy; the future Recircula Plan 2027-2035 for Waste Management in the Region of Murcia; the ERDF Programme Region of Murcia 2021-2027 (approved in December 2022); the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan of the Government of Spain (PERTE Agrifood and the urban and rural Agenda, fight against depopulation and development of agriculture - Component 3: Environmental and digital transformation of the agri-food and fisheries sector); the Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plan 2023-2027, also approved by the European Commission in 2022, where a single strategy is established that covers all CAP interventions and includes intervention 7161 "Cooperation of Operational Groups of the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-Agri)" which has among its objectives to promote the development of rural areas through the circular bioeconomy and; the Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart and Sustainable Specialisation, RIS4 Region of Murcia. Specifically, the Region of Murcia is carrying out arduous work for its sustainable development from the current Ministry of the Environment, Universities, Research and Mar Menor, with the General Directorate of the Environment; the current Ministry of Economy, Finance, European Funds and Digital Transformation, with the General Directorate of Budgets and European Funds ([The image is the logo of the European Union, featuring a circle of twelve gold stars on a blue background.](https://carmeuropa.es/fondos-ue-murcia/programa-feder-</p></div><div data-bbox=)

region-de-murcia-2021-2027/#op2); the Ministry of Water, Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, with the General Directorate of the Food Industry and Agrarian Associations (which has among its functions the promotion and support of the food industry) and; the Ministry of Business, Employment and Social Economy, with the General Directorate for the Promotion of Trade, Business Innovation and Industries and Crafts and with the Development Agency of the Region of Murcia.

And it is important to ensure consistency of activities in the area of CE implementation with activities in other areas of social and economic development in the Region of Murcia.

The agri-food sector is a fundamental pillar of the business sector in the Region of Murcia, firmly established as a leading sector in innovation, economic activity and sustainability, as outlined in the RIS4 Region of Murcia This strategic framework highlights the sector's fundamental role in driving regional growth, fostering competitiveness and addressing global challenges such as food security and climate change.

Murcia's agri-food industry is distinguished by its solid infrastructure, adoption of advanced technologies and a strong emphasis on R&D. The region's favourable climate, fertile soils and strategic geographical location have enabled it to become a leading producer and exporter of fresh produce, processed foods and high-value agricultural products. However, it is the integration of innovation and sustainability that truly sets the sector apart, aligning perfectly with the RIS4 Region of Murcia objectives of creating a smart, sustainable and inclusive regional economy.

One of the key aspects of the RIS4 Region of Murcia is its focus on value chain integration, where the agri-food sector stands out. From primary production to processing, logistics and marketing, the region has developed a highly efficient and interconnected ecosystem. Murcia's companies not only prioritise quality and safety, but also incorporate cutting-edge technologies such as precision agriculture, artificial intelligence and blockchain to optimise resource use, reduce waste and improve traceability.

The leadership of the agri-food sector in Murcia is also evident in its commitment to sustainability, a fundamental component of RIS4 Region of Murcia. By adopting practices that minimise environmental impact, such as waste recovery, the integration of renewable energy and water-efficient irrigation systems, the sector demonstrates its dedication to the principles of the CE. Agro-industrial by-products are increasingly being converted into bio-

fertilisers, feed or even bio-energy, displaying a model of resource efficiency that contributes to Murcia's reputation as an innovator in sustainable practices.

In addition, the RIS4 Region of Murcia identifies the agri-food sector as a key driver of regional employment and social cohesion. With thousands of jobs directly and indirectly linked to the industry, it serves as a pillar of economic stability and growth in Murcia. The sector also promotes rural development by supporting SMEs, cooperatives and family farms, thus ensuring a wide distribution of economic benefits across the region.

Another key factor contributing to the leadership of the agri-food sector is its ability to foster collaboration between academia, research institutions and businesses. The Region of Murcia is home to several research centres and universities that work closely with industry stakeholders to develop innovative solutions tailored to the needs of the sector. These collaborations have led to advances in areas such as biotechnology, food preservation and sustainable packaging, reinforcing Murcia's position as a leader in agri-food innovation.

Exports further underline the dominance of the agri-food sector in Murcia's economic landscape. The region is a major supplier of high-quality products to European and global markets, and has earned a reputation for excellence and reliability. Products such as fruit, vegetables and olive oil not only represent Murcia's agricultural heritage, but also its ability to adapt to changing market demands and consumer preferences. The RIS4 Region of Murcia recognises this export strength as a critical factor in improving Murcia's international competitiveness.

In conclusion, the leadership of the agri-food sector in the Region of Murcia is a testament to its ability to innovate, adapt and adopt sustainable practices. As the RIS4 Region of Murcia framework highlights, the sector is not only a key economic driver, but also a model of regional resilience and sustainability. By continuing to invest in research, technology and collaboration, the agri-food sector will remain at the forefront of Murcia's economic and social development, ensuring its position as a leader in the global agri-food industry.

In order to achieve our objective "Circular Economy in the Region of Murcia", it is intended that in the period 2025-2027 the activities that have a clear leadership will be maintained, in such a way that a path of economic growth through innovation is maintained, approaching the most prosperous and advanced regions of Spain and Europe. The activities that have a clear leadership in terms of innovation in Murcia, as well as a substantial relative weight in the regional economy, are those linked to the agri-food value chain, which include livestock,

fishing and the food industry; those linked to the water cycle (its treatment, purification and management); the environment, logistics and transport. All these activities, prioritized in a systemic way, coordinated, oriented and transformed through the intensive use of advanced technologies, will allow the Region to obtain competitive advantages. To date, the RIS4 Region of Murcia Strategy has driven growth by focusing on the most promising areas of specialisation based on their competitive advantages, through the so-called business opportunity discovery process, promoting activities with transformative potential that contribute to the future of the Region. Thus, in the funding programs related to R&D, only those that belong to a priority area of RIS4 Region of Murcia will be supported, while for Technology Transfer and innovation services, belonging to a priority area of RIS4 Region of Murcia is an important favorable criterion in the evaluation.

Finally, we cannot forget that SMEs consider innovation to be a high risk, both due to the need for financial resources and the personnel involved. For example, calculating the carbon footprint in agri-food companies means spending time implementing innovative technologies to know consumption and emissions in real time, as well as managing a large amount of information that can be used to verify the carbon footprint. Therefore, the entrepreneur is faced with the problem of assigning personnel, without specific and very limited knowledge, to tasks that do not bring "visible income", in accordance with the current situation and mentality of SMEs in the sector (without high technological capacity, average environmental awareness and limited economic resources). This problem could be solved by promoting business sustainability through external financing, as well as raising awareness among future entrepreneurs/technicians in the sector and promoting it in public events aimed at the business sector.

Therefore, within this framework, new calls for aid will be opened to improve the creation of innovative industries and the development of R&D projects, through INFO. The aim is to avoid duplications in the financing of R&D projects, as well as to optimize resources, if the topics of interest for implementing innovative technologies in the CE are known through specialized Working Groups, formed by members of the entire innovation ecosystem. In any case, the information can be obtained beyond direct sources, such as the Working Groups, or by using Technology Surveillance tools.

5 SWOT Circular Economy in the agri-food sector

The SWOT analysis shown in this section is the result of the diagnosis obtained thanks to the content of the SAT developed in the A2C project. It has been a roadmap to link dimensions and define the actions that are part of the CEAP presented.

AGROFOOD conducted a study of the measures implemented and the demands commented by some members of the quadruple helix involved in the implementation of the CE in the regional agri-food sector:

Public sector: Responsible for defining legislative frameworks, regulations, strategies and incentives to facilitate the implementation of circular practices in the agri-food sector

Private sector (agri-food companies): Acts as a direct driver by adopting sustainable practices, developing new circular products, implementing innovative technologies and improving resource efficiency.

Academic institutions and technology centres: They provide the scientific and technical knowledge necessary for innovation, applied research, technological development and specialised training that drives the circular transition.

Civil society and consumers: They are key in the demand for sustainable and responsible products, actively participating in local energy communities and promoting cultural changes towards a more CE.

Four meetings were organised and numerous telephone conversations were held to gather relevant information. Eleven members of the agri-food sector with a minimum of 10 years' experience collaborated (AGRUPAL, COMPANIES, CTNC, CIFEA DE MOLINA DE SEGURA, ETC.). The methodology of the work consisted of presenting the most characteristic dimensions and trying to direct each session to generate a brainstorming session in which the following were collected:

- i) knowledge on the current situation of the agri-food sector based on the initial dimensions (a minimum of four contributions per person were requested and their classification as Weakness, Threat, Strength and Opportunity) – SWOT analysis;

- ii) keywords linked to technological processes/products available for the agri-food sector, such as energy efficiency, external financing, etc. and grouped by dimension
- iii) Opinions on “Success stories” proposed in the session. This action sought to generate a debate not starting from scratch, since the aim was to seek to optimise the entire process. Measures from other European Action Plans were presented and it was subsequently proposed to link them with potential solutions for the Region of Murcia.

These meetings have coincided with meetings of the working group that have defined the Good Practices of Circular Economy for the agri-food sector and their subsequent telephone conversations. The use of success stories to establish improvements and propose specific actions has been a very positive approach. Knowing examples and evaluating their implementation process is advantageous for all interested parties. It has been possible to link areas of improvement with the main dimensions that allow the implementation of the CE and to highlight best practices based on activities that can be carried out by the partners of the A2C project, as well as other companies and citizens, because they are our consumers. AGROFOOD made a list of actions, which was transferred to the Working Group and an exercise of acceptance or rejection was carried out. Once it was considered accepted by 3 members, it was classified by priority. In this case, an evaluation by score from 1 (LOW) to 5 (HIGH) was used. This score was compiled in an Excel spreadsheet to quickly sum up the results and provide an assessment of the impact in terms of improvement; the urgency in terms of time; and the feasibility in the technical-economic field. In addition, during this process, it was possible to discuss the possibility of locating the same action in several places, reducing the number of dimensions. It was also revealed that there are numerous resources that can be adapted to the agri-food sector by using other Circular Economy Action Plans as a reference.

5.1 STRENGTHS

1. Good level of collaboration between knowledge centres: in the Region of Murcia there are several knowledge centres linked to the agri-food sector and auxiliary services with the capacity to actively collaborate with companies and other knowledge centres.
2. High level of knowledge in some technologies: there are technologies that have a high or medium level of penetration and an advanced TRL for the transfer of knowledge between companies and research centres.
3. Established resource management. It allows for the reduction of consumption and waste of resources in production processes. The Green and CE allows for better management of natural resources, including water, thus avoiding its depletion.
4. Recognised products in consolidated companies. The agri-food products and those of their auxiliary sectors in the Region of Murcia are known throughout the world for their high levels of quality and safety, with a strong export position in consolidated companies.
5. Growing social awareness of the green economy. The region has the capacity to generate products with higher added value through the application of knowledge and technologies for the conservation and transformation of biodiversity. There is potential to reconvert traditional sectors and activities towards the Green and CE.
6. Favorable conditions for innovation and growing entrepreneurship. The Region of Murcia continues to receive significant European funding to undertake innovative projects. There are numerous incentives for economic promotion in the territory. The network of Universities, Technology centres and research centres are facilitators of the transfer of research results and innovation processes related to the Green and CE. In

addition, the Region has a very important training structure, in which public institutions and social agents participate. In addition, there are numerous incentives for the professional qualification of workers.

7. Important research centres, technology centres and universities established in the Region of Murcia with excellent research groups and technology transfer with a long tradition in sectors related to food. Critical mass of scientific-technical personnel in the areas of the CE. Network of agricultural and agri-food research and training centres and infrastructures, as well as technology parks around sectors of opportunity for the bioeconomy that can promote the generation of new business models.
8. Easy connection between the scientific environment and companies. In a small region, scientific actors are close to companies. In addition, technology centres are the natural link between universities and other research centres and companies.
9. Knowledge, experience, human capital and technological capacity in areas of innovation related to the bioeconomy, as well as leading companies in some of them.

5.2 WEAKNESSES

1. Weak productive fabric that hinders medium-term economic viability. Small and medium-sized companies predominate, very atomized in the territory and producers of goods and services with low added value. Insufficient technological capacity, innovation and poor business cooperation hinder competitiveness and return on investment.
2. Weak labor market. A weak labor market, with a poorly qualified supply and demand, high temporary employment and minimal hiring, inequality of opportunities, etc., presenting a limited workforce for innovation management.
3. Difficulties with technology transfer: the technical and economic viability of sustainable processes is not being transferred to companies and remains in the knowledge of

research centers, which have their external financing independent of the sales of the companies.

4. Lack of cooperation between entities for reasons of confidentiality. This aspect reduces participation in collaborative projects to solve a problem in less time.
5. Low access to new technologies: in this sense, it is known that there is low penetration of technologies in companies because they do not have a meeting point with suppliers with specific machinery in the market and the centres do not have the economic resources to undertake purchases and carry out the necessary transfer of knowledge.
6. Few dissemination activities: few resources are allocated to carrying out dissemination activities among the business sector on the opportunities that the evaluation of by-products or the reduction of costs through the optimisation of processes and product diversification represent.
7. Insufficient environmental impact analysis: there are hardly any studies of the environmental impact of these processes, which are in the implementation phase.
8. Greater complexity and guarantee of supply. The principle of reusing products or components would allow different supply chains to be linked. That is, waste from one industry can serve as resources or raw materials for others. This generates a complex network of interdependencies that increases the risk. Problems in one chain are transferred to those that are directly linked to it. Furthermore, the seasonality of by-products does not guarantee a continuous uniform supply.
9. Educational and training problems. Human resources with significant deficits in management, staffing and training (eco-design, bioeconomy, valorisation, recycling, etc.), which are in the process of improvement. Lack of skills to enable sustainable actions to emerge.

10. Lack of “industrial” orientation to respond in the short term to the needs of the food industries. Large projects, excellent research articles, doctorates, etc., sometimes do not respond to the R&D demands of companies. Confidentiality must be ensured.
11. Limited communication to access consumers because entrepreneurial companies and those that innovate do not have the resources for high advertising or prefer not to divert attention from their main line of business until they have secured the launch of differentiating products on the market.

5.3 OPPORTUNITIES

1. Interesting collaboration opportunities detected by some companies, since the use of by-products usually benefits both the generators, who save costs and obtain extra income, and the recyclers, who obtain raw materials at reduced costs or for free.
2. High cost of water and energy makes it necessary to optimize them within the framework of eco-innovation. Increase in the price of conventional energy and dependence on the international price of fossil fuels, as well as the high costs and dependence on water and its treatments.
3. Regulatory and reference framework. The European Union already has a roadmap on the CE. This body has launched a package related to the CE, that is already materializing in strategies, one of the latest on plastics, and future directives. In this sense, in Spain there is the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy 2030 that details different areas of action.
4. Labor market and trend in job creation and self-employment. The European Union has highlighted the role of the green economy in the generation of new jobs in sectors related to the environment or in the improvement of environmental processes. Jobs related to

eco-design, repair or remanufacturing, and recycling of waste will gain weight thanks to the CE. The Region of Murcia promotes the creation of green jobs.

5. New business models after the global push for the Green and CE. The Green and CE, the bioeconomy and sustainable development have the political impetus of Europe, nationally and regionally, contributing to improving the environment and combating climate change. This trend generates opportunities for new economic activities, quality jobs and the rise of new related business models: industrial ecology, eco-design, territorial symbiosis, collaborative economy, bioeconomy.
6. Global ecological awareness. There is a global ecological awareness as a consequence of the raw materials crisis and global warming. This drives the growth of the green economy, the revaluation of by-products, the increase in demand for ecological products, the demand for renewable energies, waste management and the detection of new niches for employment and economic activity.
7. Lines of financing that contribute to the articulation of R&D work and the implementation of innovations in the Region of Murcia.
8. The knock-on effect of success stories in the dissemination of success stories and innovative good practices.
9. Territorial specialization strategy aimed at segments with high added value and intensive in qualified human capital.
10. New virtual geography without center or periphery. The Internet and new communication technologies have made the concepts of center and periphery disappear from the map of virtual relations that they generate. Distance does not exist in this new space and this becomes an opportunity for rural and peripheral territories such as the Region of Murcia.

5.4 THREATS

1. Lack of knowledge of the topics in a large part of the agri-food sector: many companies are unaware of the opportunities for valorising by-products and their nutritional use, both for human and animal feed, production of biomaterials, etc. This discourages R&D and limits the future industrial and commercial implementation of the solutions developed.
2. Problems with large-scale scaling and supply: scaling up new processes poses difficulties, largely because more developments are required. In addition, in terms of commercial implementation, it may be difficult to ensure the supply of some raw materials or new extracts.
3. Implementation costs: the perception of many companies is that the initial investments to start up operational lines in these topics are very expensive, which means taking on a significant risk as a return that makes them profitable is not guaranteed.
4. Lack of public aid and lack of specificity: both companies and knowledge centres indicate that more aid is needed, and that some of it is specific to the subject.
5. Lack of harmonization of standards. Due to the novelty of the concept, there is a lack of definition of standards to guarantee the development of Circular Economy Strategies. This is key to homogenizing actions for all types of industries.
6. Unrenewed mentality. The lack of environmental awareness among the different actors in the system slows down the implementation and extension of the concept of CE. Although it is true that at the consumer level a sustainable social awareness is developing, sustainability is not the decisive or priority factor in purchasing. Some of the key principles of the CE are not yet widely accepted by society. For example, remanufactured products may be a sign of poorer quality for some consumers and working with “waste” may give a bad image to the sector.
7. Strong agro-industrial competition and problems with suppliers. The agro-industrial sector is subject to the tensions of international competition and the control of

multinationals, increased by the trend of consuming low-priced products and high energy costs.

8. Increased bureaucratic demands. Bureaucracy in the region is not a unique feature; it is encouraged and accompanied by strong bureaucratic demands in all national and European administrative bodies, sometimes characterised by obstacles, lack of coordination, little flexibility, slowness and regulatory and economic restrictions.
9. High dependence on funding calls by the scientific-technical field. High dependence of research agents on calls for proposals from different types of organisations and territorial areas to obtain funding for research. Sometimes, research is directed by the topics of the calls for proposals and not by the real needs of the food processing sector.
10. Outflow of innovative talent. Few job offers and low wage costs prevent the retention of innovative talent in the Region of Murcia, reducing the potential for improvement and industrial development.

5.5 TARGET ACTIVITIES

This section presents the details of the target activities for a CE, where a clear roadmap for its implementation has been provided through more than 70 available solutions.

Target 1: Reducing Waste in Production

Activities	Solutions
Process Optimization	<i>Implementation of efficient technologies</i>
	<i>Modular and flexible production processes</i>
	<i>Minimization of waste in processing</i>
Use of Organic Waste	<i>Reuse of agri-food waste as biofuels</i>
	<i>Generation of co-products for human consumption</i>
	<i>Fertilization with organic waste</i>
	<i>Animal feed</i>

Target 2: Sustainable Product and Packaging Design

Activities	Solutions
Eco-design of Products	<i>Use of recyclable and recycled materials</i>
	<i>Reduction in material usage</i>
	<i>Reusability and modularity</i>
Reduction of Plastics and Replacement with Innovative Alternatives	<i>Biodegradable plastics</i>
	<i>Plant fiber-based packaging</i>
	<i>Edible packaging</i>
Minimizing Food Waste through Design	<i>Airtight packaging adapted to the product life cycle</i>
	<i>Portions tailored to consumer needs</i>
Encouraging the Design of Returnable and Reusable Packaging	<i>Returnable packaging</i>
	<i>Containers for reusable packaging</i>
	<i>Deposit and return systems</i>
Optimization of Transport and Logistics through Design	<i>Stackable and compact packaging</i>
	<i>Lightweight and durable packaging</i>
Sustainable and Transparent Labeling	<i>Plastic-free labels</i>
	<i>Recycling and sustainability information</i>
	<i>Eco-labels and sustainability certifications</i>

Target 3: Revalorization of Agro-industrial By-products

Activities	Solutions
Identification and Classification of By-products	<i>Waste mapping</i>
	<i>Classification of by-products based on potential</i>
Development of Products from By-products	<i>Derived food products: extracts, flours, fermented beverages, alternative protein products, organic acids, and amino acids</i>
	<i>Biotechnology for improving food quality: The use of enzymes and microbial cultures to enhance texture, flavor, and shelf life without relying on artificial chemicals</i>
Bioplastics and Biodegradable Materials	<i>Use of bioplastics and biodegradable materials</i>
Energy Generation from Waste	<i>Use of biomass and biogas</i>
Organic Fertilization and Composting	<i>Implementation of organic fertilization and composting</i>
Animal Feed	<i>Production of animal feed</i>
Industrial Applications	<i>Pharmaceutical and cosmetic products</i>
	<i>Biotechnology and fermentation</i>

Target 4: Efficiency in Water and Energy Use

Activities	Solutions
Efficient Irrigation Technologies	<i>Drip irrigation systems</i>
	<i>Automated moisture control and irrigation</i>
Heat Recovery Technologies	<i>Implementation of heat recovery technologies</i>
Renewable Energy in Agro-food Facilities	<i>Installation of solar panels</i>
	<i>Wind energy</i>
	<i>Biogas energy</i>

Target 5: Digital Technologies and Traceability for Greater Efficiency and Transparency

Activities	Solutions
Implementation of Digital Traceability	<i>Blockchain-based traceability platforms</i>
	<i>Real-time traceability software</i>
	<i>Smart labels and QR codes</i>
Optimization of Resource Use through Digitalization	<i>IoT sensors for monitoring and control</i>
	<i>Big Data and predictive analytics for supply chain management</i>
	<i>Automation of logistics and distribution</i>
Implementation of Data-based Circular Economy Systems	<i>Waste and by-product exchange platforms</i>
	<i>Digital management of the value chain</i>
Encouraging Collaborative Economy through Digital Platforms	<i>Sustainable agricultural product marketplaces (digital marketplace)</i>
	<i>Knowledge-sharing networks</i>
Innovation in Product Design with Digital Technologies	<i>3D modeling and design for packaging</i>
	<i>Life cycle simulation</i>

Target 6: Education and Training

Activities	Solutions
Awareness and Training for Producers	<i>Workshops and training on circular practices</i>
	<i>Support for the adoption of new technologies</i>
	<i>Incentive programs and certifications</i>
Consumer Education and Awareness	<i>Awareness campaigns on responsible purchasing</i>
	<i>Labeling and certification of circular products</i>

	<i>Education on food waste</i>
Awareness in the Business Sector	<i>Training on circular economy implementation in businesses</i>
	<i>Dissemination of best business practices</i>
	<i>Support in the design of sustainable products</i>
Training and Awareness for Authorities and Public Policies	<i>Workshops for authorities and policymakers</i>
	<i>Creation of regulatory frameworks for the circular economy</i>
Mass Awareness Campaigns and Continuous Education	<i>Campaigns through media and social networks</i>
	<i>Formal and informal education on sustainability</i>

Target 7: Circular and Collaborative Value Chains

Activities	Solutions
Creation of Collaboration Networks Among Producers	<i>Regional collaboration networks</i>
	<i>Waste exchange platforms</i>
Promotion of Cooperation between the Agro-food Sector and the Recycling Industry	<i>Support for advanced recycling technologies</i>
	<i>Creation of collaboration networks for waste utilization</i>
	<i>Support for circular business models</i>
Encouraging Public-Private Collaboration	<i>Joint infrastructure development and creation of innovation centers working directly with local producers</i>
	<i>Collaborative research projects</i>
	<i>Startup incubation programs</i>
Regulatory Framework and Supporting Public Policies	<i>Tax incentives for circular practices</i>
	<i>Grants for businesses</i>
	<i>Regulations on recycling and waste reduction</i>
	<i>Standards for circular product labeling</i>
Consumer Involvement in the Circular Economy	<i>Promotion of responsible consumption</i>

5.6 SWOT REVIEW

A revised SWOT is a key tool for defining lines of action in the CE, as it allows the analysis of the current situation to be transformed into concrete strategies and subsequently practical actions.

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote cooperation in innovation projects Enhance knowledge transfer Implement advanced technologies to optimize resources Improve product differentiation through sustainability Increase dissemination and awareness in society Promote economic incentives and financing lines Strengthen the relationship between technology centers and companies Create collaboration spaces to accelerate innovation Retain talent and improve training in Circular Economy (CE) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote cooperation in innovation projects Enhance knowledge transfer Implement advanced technologies to optimize resources Improve product differentiation through sustainability Increase dissemination and awareness in society Promote economic incentives and financing lines Strengthen the relationship between technology centers and companies Create collaboration spaces to accelerate innovation Retain talent and improve training in Circular Economy (CE)
OPPORTUNITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate the integration of circular economy processes Invest in energy efficiency and water optimization Align regional policies with European strategies Promote training and entrepreneurship programs in CE Encourage investment in circular businesses Boost responsible consumption and the green economy Ensure access to European and national funds Promote the replicability of successful circular models Integrate CE into all productive sectors Drive digitalization in circular models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote business training Strengthen logistics and ensure supply Establish tax incentives and financial aid Streamline administrative processes and improve funding Harmonize regulations at the regional and national levels Raise awareness in society about the benefits of CE Improve competitiveness through innovation Retain talent with incentives and better conditions

6 Circular Economy Action Plan for agri-food sector in the Region of Murcia

6.1 Action lines to achieve sustainability in the production and management of available resources

Once the SWOT analysis and the relevant objectives have been reviewed, together with the dimensions initially established within the framework of the A2C Project, we can affirm that it is possible to integrate all the information and establish some lines of action considered priorities for the Region of Murcia and use terms that are easy to use for all members of the quadruple helix.

Below are the lines of action that seek not only to reduce the environmental impact of the agri-food sector, but also to increase its competitiveness, promote innovation and

strengthen the economic resilience of the Region of Murcia. The combination of the valorisation of by-products and the optimisation of resources, the use of digital tools, the visibility and inter-sectoral collaboration will position Murcia as a benchmark in the CE in the agri-food sector.

1. Increasing Critical Mass and Internationalisation

The main objective is to increase Critical Mass in the CE in the Region of Murcia during the period 2025-2027, maintaining activities with a clear leadership in terms of innovation and economic weight. These activities include the agri-food value chain (livestock, fishing and food industry), the water cycle, the environment, logistics and transport. Through the adoption of advanced technologies and the prioritisation of resources, the aim is to position Murcia among the most advanced regions in Spain and Europe. The RIS4 Region of Murcia Strategy will be the basis for identifying and promoting areas of specialisation, encouraging the development of projects with a high transformative impact on the regional economy.

In addition, support for R&D projects in high-impact areas will be prioritised, such as the valorisation of by-products, the reduction of the carbon footprint and water eco-efficiency. These actions seek to transform the challenges of the agri-food sector into opportunities for innovation and sustainability.

Expected Impact

- ✓ Consolidation of the regional ecosystem: Greater connection and collaboration between key players will increase the efficiency and impact of local initiatives.
- ✓ Greater global visibility: Murcia's companies and entities will be better positioned to compete and innovate in an international environment.
- ✓ Development of capabilities and competitiveness: The region will benefit from broader access to advanced technologies, specialized knowledge and global markets.

2. Improving Human Capital, Training and Awareness

Strengthening human capital is essential to implement CE practices. Training and awareness-raising of companies, technicians and society in general will accelerate the transition towards circular models.

Expected Impact

- ✓ Increased adoption of sustainable practices: Businesses and society will be better informed and empowered to implement circular models.
- ✓ Generation of green employment: Preparing the labour market for opportunities in circularity, driving sustainable economic development.
- ✓ Cultural transformation: Building a more conscious, sustainable and committed region with the CE.

3. Improved Governance and Access to Finance

Optimizing access to financial resources and fostering coordination among stakeholders is critical. Improved governance will ensure that efforts are aligned and resources are leveraged efficiently.

Expected Impact

- ✓ Increased implementation of CE projects: Companies in the agri-food sector will have greater access to financing and technical resources, facilitating their transition towards circular models.
- ✓ Strengthening regional competitiveness: Improved governance and financing will allow the agri-food sector to consolidate its position as a leader in circular innovation in Spain and Europe.
- ✓ Optimisation of public and private resources: By avoiding duplications and improving coordination between actors, a more efficient use of available financial resources will be guaranteed.

4. Improved Standardisation and Legislation

The development of specific regulations and clear standards will allow for a more effective implementation of the CE in the agri-food sector.

Expected Impact

- ✓ Clarity in the regulatory framework: The publication of relevant regulations will facilitate legal compliance by companies in the agri-food sector, avoiding sanctions and encouraging the implementation of good practices.
- ✓ Reduction of uncertainty for companies: By knowing in advance the current requirements and regulations, companies will be able to plan their investment and adaptation strategies with greater certainty.
- ✓ Facilitation of access to financing: Companies that comply with CE regulations will be better positioned to access European, national and regional funds for sustainability.
- ✓ Generation of trust in consumers and companies: Standards will help ensure that circular products meet technical, health and environmental requirements, promoting their demand.
- ✓ Facilitation of exports: Alignment with national and international standards will favor the commercialization of circular products in global markets, strengthening the competitiveness of Murcia.
- ✓ Attracting investments: A clear and favorable regulatory framework for the CE will make Murcia an attractive destination for investment in sustainable technologies and circular production.
- ✓ Optimizing the use of public and private resources: By having centralized and accessible information on regulations and standards, duplications will be avoided and strategic planning in the region will be improved.
- ✓ Better communication between companies, administration and scientific institutions: The creation of mechanisms for standardization and regulatory dissemination will facilitate cooperation between the different actors in the innovation and sustainability ecosystem.

6.2 Improving Critical Mass and Internationalization

Improving critical mass and internationalisation within the framework of the Circular Economy Action Plan for the agri-food sector of the Region of Murcia seeks to consolidate the region's position as a benchmark in innovation, sustainability and competitiveness at national and international level. This involves strengthening local capacities, generating synergies between key actors and projecting the initiatives and achievements of the Region of Murcia towards a global environment.

Given the strategic importance of the agri-food sector in the regional economy and its leadership in areas such as water management, waste recovery and the development of food technologies, it is crucial to expand participation and collaboration in international networks, while strengthening the local base through initiatives that integrate research, innovation and business development.

Working Groups have been created from the INFO with companies and researchers, among other agents of the R&D ecosystem to identify transformative itineraries, within the framework of the RIS4 Region of Murcia to facilitate the Green Transition. Issues such as the valorisation of by-products, water eco-efficiency, the reduction of the carbon footprint, etc. are topics of interest to companies and researchers, and are part of the areas of specialisation of the RIS4 Region of Murcia. In the Agri-Food Working Group, aspects of the need to implement the CE have been discussed due to the high generation of waste, by-products, in addition to water consumption and discharge, and emissions from boilers that feed the thermal processes of the agri-food sector, etc. Agri-food leadership is a priority in the RIS4 Region of Murcia 2021-2027, and therefore R&D actions will be carried out to support companies and researchers, as well as the technological entrepreneurship of companies based on transformative technologies. Some of the actions that have been carried out and are currently being promoted are:

- Support for business R&D for Sustainability
- Support for R&D in Technological Centres for Sustainability
- Vouchure “Sustainability of business products and processes”

In this way, it is expected to improve R&D activities based on transformative technologies and to support the creation of innovative industries.

6.2.1 Actions

1. Creation of an inventory with entities linked to the agri-food sector and the Circular Economy

The lack of visibility and connection between local actors limits the ability to generate critical mass in the region. This inventory will allow:

To identify and connect key players: Companies, technology centres, universities and public bodies will be able to collaborate more effectively on CE projects.

To facilitate coordination of efforts: By having a clear vision of the available resources and capabilities, integrated strategies can be designed to maximize impact.

To optimize the use of resources: This will avoid duplications and encourage collaboration rather than competition between entities.

Entities involved: CTNC, INFO

Schedule: 2025-2027

2. Creation of the Circular Economy Working Subgroup in the Agri-Food Working Group

The formation of this subgroup will allow us to specifically address the challenges and opportunities of the Circular Economy in the agri-food sector. This group will be key to:

Promoting thematic specialization: It will allow us to focus our efforts on critical areas such as the valorization of by-products, water eco-efficiency and waste management.

Coordinating collaborative projects: It will serve as a space to identify synergies and develop joint initiatives.

Generating specialized knowledge: It will facilitate the transfer of knowledge and the exchange of best practices between the actors in the sector.

Entities involved: INFO

Schedule: 2025-2027

3. R&D Aid Lines with a collaborative aspect and a Circular Economy context

Access to financing for R&D projects is essential to promote innovation in the Circular Economy. These aid lines will allow:

Stimulate public-private collaboration: Encourage joint projects between companies, technology centres and universities.

Promote transformative innovation: Support initiatives that generate an impact on the sustainability and competitiveness of the agri-food sector.

Reduce economic barriers: Facilitate the participation of SMEs in innovative projects that they would otherwise not be able to undertake.

Entities involved: INFO, CARM

Schedule: 2025-2027

4. Technology Transfer and Technology Monitoring Services

Access to advanced technologies and knowledge is key to boosting the competitiveness of the sector. These services will allow:

Identifying global trends: Through technology monitoring reports, companies will be able to anticipate changes in the market and regulations.

Accelerating the adoption of technologies: Technology transfer services will facilitate the incorporation of innovative solutions in production processes.

Promoting the generation of value: Connecting research with the real needs of the market, ensuring that the technologies developed are applicable and useful.

Entities involved: TTCCs, INFO

Schedule: 2026-2027

5. Establishing collaboration and communication with Technology Platforms

Technology platforms, such as the PTF4LS and the Interplatform Group for Circular Economy, offer a space for collaboration at a national and international level. Integration into these platforms will allow:

Connecting Murcia with global networks: Expanding the scope of projects developed in the region and generating new opportunities for cooperation.

Accessing advanced knowledge: Technology platforms are a key source of information on trends, technologies and best practices.

Increasing regional competitiveness: By participating in these networks, the Region of Murcia will be able to position itself as a leader in the CE.

Entities involved: AGROFOOD, TTCCs, universities, private sector	Schedule: 2025-2027
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6. Creation of an International Network in Circular Economy

The creation of an International network through key events such as Murcia Food and the International Symposium on Food and Circular Technologies will allow:

Promoting internationalization: Giving visibility to the initiatives and achievements of the Region of Murcia in the field of CE.

Promoting international collaboration: Establishing strategic alliances with other regions, companies and institutions at a global level.

Promoting networking: Creating spaces for the exchange of knowledge and the generation of business opportunities.

Entities involved: INFO, CTNC, AGROFOOD	Schedule: 2025-2027
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7. Participation in international fairs and events

International fairs and events are an essential platform to project the Murcia agri-food sector towards global markets. This participation will allow:

Positioning the regional brand: Showing Murcia's capabilities and achievements in innovation and sustainability.

Establishing strategic contacts: Generating alliances with international partners that promote the development of the sector.

Accessing new market opportunities: Expanding the reach of circular products and services developed in the region.

Entities involved: INFO, CARM, TTCCs, private sector	Schedule: 2025-2027
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6.3 Improvement of Human Capital, Training and Education

The improvement of Human Capital, Training and Education within the framework of the Circular Economy Action Plan for the agri-food sector of the Region of Murcia is based on the need to develop skills, raise awareness in society and promote a cultural change that facilitates the adoption of circular practices. The success of the CE depends not only on technology and financial resources, but also on the ability of people and organizations to understand, apply and lead this sustainable model.

6.3.1 Actions

1. Sustainability and Circular Economy Conference

Loop Murcia: I Circular Economy Fair. Murcia hosted the first circular economy fair within the framework of Loop Murcia between February 6 and 13, 2022. This was the first action related to the Circular Economy Strategy approved in 2021 that was launched and allowed the creation of a framework for dialogue and exhibition of circular economy projects that involve companies at local, regional and national level, supported by business and circular economy associations and organizations working in the Region of Murcia.

The lack of knowledge about the principles and benefits of the Circular Economy in the agri-food sector limits its adoption. The thematic conferences allow:

Disseminating good practices and success stories: Companies, researchers and administrations can share experiences that serve as inspiration for other actors.

Generating networking spaces: Facilitating the exchange of ideas and the creation of alliances between companies, technology centers and universities.

Updating knowledge: Providing training on new regulations, technologies and trends related to sustainability and circularity.

Entities involved: AGROFOOD, CIFEA Molina de Segura, CRN Conservas Vegetales, AEMARM, CTNC, CETEC, UM, UPCT, UCAM, CARM, CAJAMAR, FUNDACION SÉNECA, INFO

Schedule: 2026-2027

2. Promotion of the Guide to Good Practices in the Agri-Food Sector in the Circular Economy

Many companies, especially SMEs, lack clear guidelines on how to implement the Circular Economy in their processes. This guide will allow:

Establishing practical references: Providing concrete and applicable examples to the agri-food sector, from the valorisation of by-products to the optimisation of the use of resources.

Promoting standardisation: Helping companies align their practices with national and international standards in circularity.

Promoting sectoral commitment: Promoting the adoption of these good practices as part of corporate social responsibility.

Entities involved: AGROFOOD

Schedule: 2025-2026

3. Infoday on the Circular Economy in the agri-food sector

Information events (Infodays) are essential to give visibility to the opportunities offered by the Circular Economy. This type of activity will allow:

Presenting available programs and aid: Informing companies about financing lines, regulations and projects in which they can participate.

Promoting collaboration: Facilitating the meeting between different actors in the innovation ecosystem for the development of joint projects.

Raising awareness: Showing the positive impact of the CE on the competitiveness and sustainability of the sector.

Entities involved: INFO, CTNC

Schedule: 2025-2027

4. Green Jobs Observatory for the agri-food sector

Green jobs are one of the great opportunities of the CE, but they require continuous analysis to identify trends and opportunities. This observatory will allow:

Monitoring the labour market: Identifying the needs for skills and competencies in the agri-food sector.

Designing specific training programmes: Based on market demands, ensuring that workers and future professionals are prepared for the challenges of circularity.	
Promoting employability: Facilitating the creation of sustainable jobs in areas such as waste management, clean technologies and circular production.	
Entities involved: AGROFOOD, CTNC	Schedule: 2026-2027

5. Press releases, blog posts and newsletters on the Circular Economy

Effective communication is key to raising awareness in society and promoting a cultural shift towards sustainability. These actions will allow:

Increasing the visibility of circular initiatives: Disseminating progress, projects and success stories through different channels.

Continuing education: Informing society about the benefits and opportunities of the CE.

Strengthening the link between science, technology and society: Showing how innovation can transform the agri-food sector.

Entities involved: INFO, CARM, CTNC, CETEC, private sector	Schedule: 2025-2027
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6. Dissemination of the results of funded R&D&I projects

It is essential that technological advances and solutions developed in the field of the Circular Economy reach the business sector and society in general. This dissemination will allow:

Sharing knowledge: Showing how funded projects have generated tangible benefits in terms of sustainability and innovation.

Promoting replicability: Inspiring other companies and institutions to adopt similar practices.

Strengthening public support: Raising awareness about the importance of investing in R&D for sustainable development.

Entities involved: private sector, TTCCs, INFO, CARM, UM, UPCT, UCAM	Schedule: 2025-2027
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7. Raising awareness in society and information resources

A shift towards circular models requires the involvement of the whole of society. Raising awareness through corporate social responsibility agreements and information resources will allow:

Creating collective awareness: Educating about the environmental impact of the agri-food sector and how circularity can mitigate it.

Promoting citizen participation: Encouraging responsible behaviour in consumption and waste management.

Strengthening the image of the sector: Showing the commitment of companies to sustainability and innovation.

Entities involved: private sector, AGROFOOD, TTCCs, INFO, CARM	Schedule: 2025-2027
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8. School campaign to promote circular and responsible consumption

Education from an early age is key to building a more sustainable society. This campaign will allow:

Encouraging responsible habits: Teaching young people about the impact of their consumption decisions on the environment.

Creating intergenerational awareness: Promoting the circular economy as a model for the future both at home and in the community.

Ensuring the continuity of the circular model: Training future generations of conscious professionals and consumers.

Entities involved: CTNC, AGROFOOD, CETEC, PRIMAFRIO	Schedule: 2025-2027
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6.4 Improving Governance and Access to Financing

Improving Governance and Access to Financing within the framework of the Circular Economy Action Plan for the agri-food sector in the Region of Murcia focuses on overcoming the administrative, economic and coordination barriers that hinder the implementation of circular practices by companies and entities. This line of action seeks to strengthen the

articulation between the different actors in the innovation ecosystem (companies, technology centres, universities and public administrations) and guarantee efficient access to financial resources that allow progress in the transition towards a circular model.

The actions have been designed to address the main barriers that limit effective governance and access to financing in the agri-food sector, contributing to:

- Optimising coordination between key actors: The creation of digital tools and specialised units facilitates collaboration between companies, technology centres and public administrations.
- Improving access to financial resources: By centralising and disseminating information on aid and calls for proposals, companies will have greater possibilities of accessing financing to implement circular models.
- Strengthening the sector's capacity for innovation: Technical and administrative support for national and European calls for proposals will promote the development of high-impact sustainability projects.

6.4.1 Actions

1. Creation of a website section that brings together Circular Economy Strategy documents for the agri-food sector

The lack of centralised access to information on strategies, regulations and resources related to the Circular Economy creates a knowledge gap and makes it difficult for companies, researchers and entrepreneurs to make informed decisions. A centralised website will allow:

Facilitating access to information: It will bring together key documents, such as regional, national and European strategies, relevant regulations and success stories, in one place.

Promoting transparency: It will allow companies and agents in the sector to know the strategic priorities and how to align with them to maximise their financing and development opportunities.

Promoting collaboration: As a shared space, the website will facilitate interaction between actors in the agri-food sector and the Circular Economy, promoting synergies and joint projects.

Entities involved: AGROFOOD

Schedule: 2026-2027

2. Creation of a unit to publicise calls for aid aimed at companies and send alerts to users

Access to financing is one of the biggest challenges for SMEs in the agri-food sector, as many are unaware of the available calls or do not have the resources to analyse which ones are relevant to their projects. This unit will allow:

Increasing the visibility of opportunities: It will disseminate calls for aid through personalised alerts, facilitating access to financing for Circular Economy projects.

Reducing the administrative burden on companies: By having clear and centralised information, companies will be able to focus on preparing their proposals instead of looking for sources of financing.

Promoting participation in sustainable projects: By highlighting financing lines aligned with the Circular Economy, the implementation of circular technologies and processes in companies will be encouraged.

Entities involved: CTNC

Schedule: 2025-2027

3. Support for companies in National and European calls for proposals with Sustainability lines

Access to international financing, especially at the European level, is a key opportunity for the development of the agri-food sector in Murcia. However, many companies lack the technical or administrative knowledge to submit competitive proposals. This support will allow:

Facilitate participation in European programs such as Horizon Europe, Interreg or LIFE: It will provide technical assistance to prepare projects aligned with sustainability and circularity objectives.

Maximize the use of available resources: It will help companies identify the most appropriate calls for proposals and prepare solid proposals that increase the probability of success.

Promote international cooperation: By participating in European calls, companies will be able to establish alliances with international partners, accessing new markets and advanced knowledge.	
Entities involved: CTNC, CETEC, AGROFOOD, INFO	Schedule: 2025-2027

6.5 Improved Standardization and Legislation

The improvement of standardisation and legislation in the field of the Circular Economy for the agri-food sector in the Region of Murcia arises from the need to guarantee a clear regulatory framework and tools that facilitate the implementation of circular models. This approach seeks to establish a solid foundation so that companies, institutions and entities in the agri-food sector can effectively adopt sustainable practices, reducing the administrative and technical barriers that currently limit their adoption.

6.5.1 Actions

1. Regional inventory of agri-food by-products and waste

The agri-food sector generates a large volume of by-products and waste with potential for valorisation, but in many cases these resources are not identified or classified adequately. The lack of a regional inventory makes it difficult to exploit them and create secondary markets for their reuse. This inventory will allow:

Identifying valorisation opportunities: It will facilitate the development of innovative initiatives, such as bio-ingredients, bioplastics, bio-fertilisers or bio-energy, using specific by-products from the sector.

Promoting transparency and access to data: Companies, research centres and other entities will be able to access precise information on the availability of materials that can be reused or transformed.

Optimising decision-making: It will serve as a key tool for designing regional policies and strategies focused on the Circular Economy.

Entities involved: CTNC, AGROFOOD, AGRUPAL	Schedule: 2025-2027
<p>2. Creation of a Working Group to explore the standardisation of new products</p> <p>The lack of clear standards for products obtained through circular processes (such as bioplastics or food additives from by-products) limits their acceptance in the market and generates uncertainty among producers and consumers. This working group will allow:</p>	
<p>Defining quality and safety criteria: It will establish technical standards for products derived from circular processes, guaranteeing their compatibility with national and international standards.</p>	
<p>Facilitating market entry: Standardisation reduces the risks associated with marketing and promotes the acceptance of circular products in different industries.</p>	
<p>Fostering consumer confidence: By ensuring that products meet quality and sustainability requirements, their demand is boosted in national and international markets.</p>	
Entities involved: TTCCs, AGRUPAL	Schedule: 2026-2027

<p>3. Publicity of relevant regulations linked to the Circular Economy and their impact on the sector</p> <p>The Circular Economy is an area in constant evolution, with regulations that change rapidly at regional, national and European level. Many companies, especially SMEs, have difficulties in keeping up with these regulations, which limits their ability to adapt and comply with the requirements. Publicity of relevant regulations will allow:</p>	
<p>Reducing regulatory uncertainty: Companies will be able to easily access updated information on laws and regulations related to the Circular Economy, such as recycling requirements, carbon emissions or waste recovery.</p>	
<p>Facilitating regulatory compliance: By being informed, companies will be able to proactively integrate regulatory changes into their processes, avoiding sanctions and taking advantage of opportunities.</p>	
<p>Promoting the adoption of sustainable practices: By knowing the advantages of regulations (such as incentives or tax exemptions), companies will be more willing to implement circular models.</p>	
Entities involved: TTCCs	Schedule: 2025-2027

6.6 Implementation, monitoring and financing of CEAP

The implementation of individual actions provided in the CEAP will be carried out by the entities indicated in the tables of actions. A sufficient time frame has been established to obtain a return in the period 2025-2027.

Monitoring of CE is a major challenge due to its complexity, which includes policies covering multiple areas and the interdependence between them, and due to the multidimensional impact of this transition on the socioeconomic development of the Region.

When the project is finished, the document with the Action Plan to be executed will be distributed and a follow-up will be carried out to assess whether it is being fulfilled. In that case, we will ask the partners or entities involved in each action whether they are doing it or not and why, and also evaluate its impact or return for the Region of Murcia (in terms of projects in progress, investments or any other data that they want to provide us).

Therefore, within the framework of the CEAP, a separate action has been identified to develop a conceptual approach to monitoring CE in Region of Murcia: "*To continue this line of work of the A2C project so that the AGROFOOD Murcia cluster develops two methodologies which would allow for evaluation of 1) the progress of transformation towards CE in Region of Murcia and 2) the impact of CE on social and economic development at the regional level.*"

The CEAP has not been assigned a separate framework for financing since the document identifies actions to be taken only by entities related in order to create appropriate general framework for the transfer to CE in the Region of Murcia for the agrifood sector.

The actions proposed in the CEAP concern mainly analytical, conceptual, informational, promotional and coordination tasks in the areas within the competence of individual entities. The concept of CE is firmly established in the regional strategic documents. CE will be reflected in particular in investments and actions aimed at innovation, research, development and formation.

The implementation of CE can be financed from other sources of public and private sector funding, such as new projects. In the future, if such changes are introduced to the

management system, financing can be provided from their own budgets. The implementation of CE will require commitment of the staff with regard to the entities responsible for various actions included in this CEAP.

7 Conclusions

The A2C project has been designed to boost the territorial development of circular solutions by providing tools and knowledge on how to implement these solutions. The project activities related to this task (T.7.5) and deliverable (D.7.11) have focused on defining priority lines of action and specific actions within the 2025-2027 framework.

AGROFOOD has relied on the information collected and supported by the self-assessment tool to progressively build the CEAP. A SWOT analysis has also been used to identify the framework and establish priority lines of action in accordance with the identified areas of improvement thanks to the SAT. The direct participation of CARM, INFO, PROEX, PRIMA and other partners and stakeholders has been achieved for a possible successful implementation in the future.

The CEAP is a document containing information reviewed and directed to the Region of Murcia, but replicable to other regions. Knowledge from the regional agri-food sector itself has been used to determine the aspects with potential for improvement and to optimise the resources available in the Region, such as financial aid, training capacities, dissemination and communication events, etc.

By using the CEAP Region of Murcia, other regions and cities can copy circular economy initiatives, allowing them to respond to areas for improvement.

The development of the CEAP has required a deep search for information in the Regional Strategic Programmes to understand their scope and to land the information in concrete and real actions to address them from the agri-food sector. Thanks to the knowledge of the publicly available documents and the consultation, it has been possible to compile all the information of interest and indicate achievable actions that must have a high impact to improve the critical mass, the training of future technicians in the sector, as well as the acquisition of external financing and the requirements for the exploitation of results mainly. The Sustainability aspect is very consolidated in Europe, but there are so many objectives that decision-making must be very well analysed. In many cases, actions are not addressed, such as including more efficient machinery, waste recovery, digitalising processes, etc. due to the technical or economic difficulty within the business fabric. If we talk about the impact of processes and savings in rates, there are also limitations because emissions, raw materials, etc. can be quantified, but it is necessary to allocate resources to the R&D

associated with it and many companies do not have the knowledge to execute them. In carrying out this action, it has been learned that facilitating meeting points to discuss ideas among members of the quadruple helix is the most effective way to understand the supply and demand of solutions to implement the Circular Economy in our sector.

In short, there are currently many solutions available on the market, but not all companies have access to them due to the necessary investments in terms of financial and human resources, as well as time. All this is reflected in the fact that most of them are not implemented and we are still far from a Circular Economy established in the agri-food sector in a comprehensive manner. Facilitating interlocutors speeds up the entire process.

In addition, during the development of the Plan we have encountered concepts that have been difficult to understand by stakeholders and that therefore delayed the results to be achieved. A more adapted language has been used to facilitate understanding and decide the relationship between the multidimensional model and the priority lines of action.

Stakeholders have participated in cordial conversations during work meetings and individual meetings to identify the weaknesses, strengths, threats and opportunities to implement the CE in the agri-food sector.

In addition, it can be said that events such as Circular Economy fairs -LOOP, Circularmente or Green and Circular Entrepreneurship Meetings that have been carried out in the Region of Murcia have been potential suppliers of information. Other national and international events such as Alibetopías are also considered networking activities through which it has been possible to speak with stakeholders and learn their point of view in order to attract specific measures and actions to improve the implementation of the CE in the agri-food sector of the Region of Murcia.

This action has resulted in a diagnosis and an Action Plan based on priority lines of action, so our methodology is replicable and transferable to other regions. Points for improvement must be detected with a SWOT analysis as a previous step to an Action Plan, and for this it is advisable to use self-diagnosis tools such as the SAT developed within the framework of A2C. Subsequently, a multidisciplinary working group specialized in the subject must be set up to review each of the points and establish priorities. Finally, knowing the measures already implemented in the Region or territory, with potential use, is the fastest option to optimize resources. Starting a job from scratch takes more time and resources than grouping efforts in actions that are already consolidated and allow for a faster response and visibility.

Working teams that are already specialists in CE and know the agri-food sector must be considered as members of working groups to contribute their knowledge both in processes of calls for Aid, as well as in processes of training programs, among others.

The successful implementation of a CEAP for the agri-food sector requires a multi-faceted approach that integrates financial incentives, regulatory support, stakeholder collaboration, and knowledge dissemination. By addressing critical mass, internationalization, governance, financing, training, and legislation, the Region of Murcia can establish itself as a benchmark in agri-food sustainability. This transition will not only reduce environmental impact but also create new economic opportunities, enhance competitiveness, and ensure long-term resilience in the sector.

This document is a tool for avoiding duplications and optimizing the resources of research centers, universities and technology centers aimed at responding to companies and consumers.

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